

INDIAN TELECOM INDUSTRY: A CASE STUDY OF AIRTEL AND VODAFONE IN NCR DELHI

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Abstract:

The telecom industry in India has witnessed tremendous growth since 1991. After liberalization and globalization of Indian economy, the telecom sector has witnessed dramatic changes not only with an ever-increasing subscriber base but also to provide competitive services to their subscriber in the rates. The present study tried to compare the Vodafone and Airtel on the basis of ten measure of Brand Equity. The Sample of 200 respondents has been taken from NCR. After analyzing the data, it has been found that Airtel leads in five brand equity measures (satisfaction/loyalty, perceived quality, leadership & popularity, organizational associations, market share) as compare to Vodafone. The other three measures (brand personality, brand awareness, market price and distribution coverage) have been shared by both Airtel and Vodafone. The Study has concluded that the Brand Equity of Air tel is higher than the Vodafone.

Key words: NCR, Telecom, Brand equity, Loyalty

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Introduction:

Mobile Telephony is an automatic, battery, two-way radio communication system. It is connected via radio signals to a nearby base station of the mobile telephone network. The cellular system comprises of the mobile handset and the mobile network. The mobile network has an inevitable role in the functioning of cellular communication. The cellular mobile network consists of the three major elements:

- ⇒ Mobile Switching Centre (MSC)
- ⇒ Transmission segment consisting of wireless lines between mobile handsets and the base trans-receiver handset.
- ⇒ Microwave link connecting the base station to the mobile switch and the mobile handset used of the customer.

The entire service area is divided into a series of hexagonal cells in a honeycomb pattern. That is why the name cellular. The size of the cells varies by the anticipated usage in that area. These may range in diameter from 40mtr. To 50 Km. Every cell has its own transmitting and receiving centre called the base station. These stations are connected to the mobile switching centre (MSC) through antennae. The MSC keeps track on all the subscribers and on that their cells and provides connection to the telecommunication networks. As one moves from one cell to another, the base station automatically reroutes the call to the cell that the user is entering. All this happens in split seconds without the user being aware of it.

Mobile technology is available in analog and digital. India has started straight the digital technology and accepted an International Standard called GSM (Global System for Mobile Communication) based on European specification

COMPANY PROFILE

VODAFONE

Hutch (now Vodafone) is the brand name of Hutchison Essar. It established its presence in India in 1994 and was one of the first cellular providers in the city of Mumbai. Over time it has expanded operations across the country and is one of the most respected cellular service providers known for providing world class and innovative services. Vodafone established its

presence in India in 1994 by acquiring the cellular license for Mumbai. It now has operations in 16 circles accounting for 70% of India's mobile subscriber base.

Vodafone, with about 16.67 million subscribers, is one of the most reputed telecom companies in India. Over the years, it has been named the 'Most Respected Telecom Company', the 'Best Mobile Service in the country', and the 'Most Creative and Most Effective Advertiser of the Year'.

The Vodafone Group is one of India's largest corporate houses with interests spanning the manufacturing and service sectors like Steel, Oil & Gas, Power, Telecom & BPO, Shipping & Logistics and Engineering & Constructions. The Group has an asset base of over Rs 20 billion (US\$ 4.4 billion) and employs over 4000 people.

AIRTEL

Airtel comes to you from Bharti Cellular Ltd. A consortium of giants in the telecommunication business.

Airtel launched its services in Delhi on November 14, 1995. It has at present over Six lakh fifty thousand customers in its seven years of pursuit of greater customer satisfaction, Airtel has redefined the business through marketing innovations, continuous technological up gradation of the network, introduction of new generation value added services and the highest standard of customer care.

Airtel has consistently set the benchmarks for the Indian cellular industry to follow.

- ⇒ First to launch Cellular service in Delhi on November 1995.
- ⇒ First operator to revolutionize the concept of retailing with the inauguration of Airtel Connect (exclusive showrooms) in 1995. Today Airtel has 20 Customer Care Touch points called "Connects" and over 350 dealers in Delhi and NCR towns.

AWARDS

Consecutively for four years 1997, 1998, 1999 and 2000, AirTel has been voted as the Best Cellular Service in the country and won the coveted Techies award.

- ⇒ The Asia Pacific Award for the Most Innovative HR practices-2000.
- ⇒ The Golden Peacock National Training Award for excellence in Training practices-2000.

⇒ Born a leader, the first cellular service in Delhi, Airtel has maintained leadership through constant innovations which have redefined standards of cellular services in India.

TELECOM REGULATORY AUTHORITY OF INDIA

TARIFF PLANS WITH LIFETIME VALIDITY FEATURES OF LIFE TIME TYPE TARIFF PLANS

Most operators have offered lifetime validity scheme in the prepaid segment. Few operators have also extended the concept of lifetime validity to postpaid tariff plans as well. Many operators have filed such tariff schemes with TRAI. Information on these schemes are also available in the websites of the service providers. The following are the general features applicable for tariff schemes with lifetime validity.

In the prepaid plans, the lifetime validity entails a subscriber to enjoy incoming calls for an indefinite period in lieu of an upfront payment. Whereas in the postpaid plans the lifetime concept implies that the subscriber availing these plans need not pay compulsory fixed charges like monthly rental.

The upfront payment involved in the prepaid plans with life time validity is around Rs.1000/-. A talk time content in the range ofRs.25/- to Rs.100/- is also available for the subscribers.

Most operators have extended full talk time in all subsequent recharges for such subscribers with lifetime validity. Few operator shave made provision for choice of any other available tariff schemes by subscribers who opt for lifetime validity schemes.

Some operators have prescribed minimum of one outgoing call or incoming call or a recharge to be effected in a period of 6 months as a precondition for continued connectivity. Some operators have mandated recharge within a period of six months for continuity of the lifetime scheme.

Objective of the Study: The objective of the study is to compare the Airtel and Vodafone on the basis of ten measures of brand equity - the Brand Equity Ten (BET).

Loyalty Measures

- (1) Price Premium
- (2) Satisfaction/ Loyalty

Perceive Quality/ Leadership Measures

- (3) Perceived Quality
- (4) Leadership and Popularity

Association/Differentiation Measures

- (5) Perceived Value
- (6) Brand Personality
- (7) Organizational Associations

Awareness Measures

- (8) Brand Awareness

Market Behavior Measures

- (9) Market Share
- (10) Market Price & Distribution Coverage

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design: A research design is purely and simply the framework or plan for a study that guides the collection and analysis of data. The Survey Research was used in this project, because consumer's feedback was necessary for obtaining the data.

Data Sources: Primary Data was collected by the questionnaire based market survey. Secondary Data was obtained from journals, magazines, newspapers, books and the internet.

Research Instrument:

For doing the survey research, Structured Questionnaire with both open-ended and closed-ended questions was used.

Mode of Survey:

The mode of survey was Personal Interview with the respondents during the filling up of the questionnaires.

Sampling:

The sampling used for this study was probability sampling. Since the study is only meant for certain specific categories within the total population (cell phone users, in this case), a stratified random sample was used.

Sampling

A sample size of 200 respondents is used for the study

Sampling Unit:

This study was basically an opinion survey of the residents of Delhi who are cell phone users, about the cellular service providers.

Place of Study:

Delhi and NCR

Data Analysis and Interpretation

(i) What is your Age?

15-25	37%
25-35	58%
35-45	3%
45 and Above	2%

(ii) What is your Sex?

Male	75%
Females	25%

(iii) What is your Occupation?

Business	10%
Student	50%
Govt. Servant	15%
Housewife	0%
Self Employed	7%
Others	18%

Question-1 which Cellular Service Provider are you associated with?

The first question of the study intends to find out about the cellular connection and the service provider. Since the target segments are the cellular users, all the respondents have cellular connections.

In terms of the service provider, the break up is:-

- ⇒ Vodafone----- 35%
- ⇒ Airtel----- 40%
- ⇒ Others----- 25%

Question-2 what type of connection do you use for your cell phone?

⇒ Pre paid

⇒ Post paid

The Second question is to find out the category of connection used.

Overall, the results show:-

⇒ Post Paid = 38.33 %

⇒ Pre Paid = 61.67 %

This break up in terms of services providers is as shown below

Vodafone

Post Paid	39.5 %
Pre Paid Card	60.5 %

Air Tel

Post Paid (SIM Card)	34.38 %
Pre Paid Card (Cash Card)	65.63 %

The results clearly show that there is a larger subscriber base in the pre-paid (cash card) segment, which is in consonance with the industry figures

Question-3 what are the key factors/reasons for your association with the current cellular service provider?

- ⇒ Awareness of the Service provider
- ⇒ Friends Recommended
- ⇒ Retailer Influenced
- ⇒ Advertisements Influenced
- ⇒ Market share of the service provider
- ⇒ Other reasons

The Third question intends to find out the reason for the selection of the service provider - in other words, the consumer behavior.

	Vodafone	Airtel
Awareness of the Service provider	40.61 %	42%
Friends Recommended	21.88 %	20%
Retailer Influenced	6.25 %	7%
Advertisements Influenced	12.5 %	15%
Market share of the service provider	35%	40%
Other reasons	15.63 %	12%

Almost 41 % of the Vodafone customers and 42% of Airtel customers were aware of the service and so chose it. Other reasons given by the respondents varied from gifts by relatives to company provided phone. These accounted for 15.63 % of subscribers.

Question-4 Are you aware that the following cellular companies are operating in NCR Delhi?

Brand awareness of Service Provider

The fourth question was to check the brand awareness of the customers. It would reflect the presence of the brand in their minds.

The options given were:-

Air Tel	Spice	Aircel
Vodafone	Command	Skycell
Dolphin	Escotel	BPL Mobile

The service providers of Delhi are Air Tel, Vodafone and Dolphin (MTNL). Only 30% of the customers were aware of this. The large majority, 53.33% of the respondents, said that only Air Tel and Vodafone operated Delhi. About 6.67% felt only Vodafone operated, while another 5% gave multiple options, which included both Air Tel and Vodafone.

Question-5 Are you satisfied with the services of your current cellular service provider?

The fifth question was to measure the customer **satisfaction** in terms of the service provided by the cellular operators.

Option	Airtel	Vodafone
i) Very satisfied	9.37%	8.55%
ii) Satisfied	62.5%	60.71%
iii) Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	28.13%	27.43%
iv) Dissatisfied	-	3.31%
v) Strongly dissatisfied	-	

In terms of satisfaction level, we have 9.37% of Air Tel customers who are very satisfied compared to 8.55% of Vodafone. The majority of the subscribers are a satisfied lot with 62.5% of Air Tel and 60.71% of Vodafone. In terms of dissatisfaction, Air Tel fared better with no subscribers dissatisfied while 3.31% of Vodafone subscribers showed dissatisfaction which should be considered very seriously by Vodafone.

Question-6 Kindly assesses the perceived value in terms of the tariffs / rentals for the cellular services used by you.

The sixth question was to find out the perceived value in terms of the tariffs / rentals for the cellular services

Tariffs/ Rentals	Air Tel	Vodafone
1. Very high	25%	25%
2. High	53.13%	42.86%
3. Neither high nor low	9.38%	21.43%
4. Moderate	12.5%	7.14%
5. Low	-	-
6. Cannot say	-	3.57%

The observation from this question is that Air Tel is perceived to be expensive by its customers. 53.13% of Air Tel’s customers consider the tariffs high compared to 42.86% of others. The consistent responses by Vodafone’s Cell phone’s customer show that they perceive it as a value - for -money service.

Question-7 Are you loyal to your current brand of mobile service provider?

The seventh question intends to find out the loyalty measures in terms of price premium, i.e. the price the customer will pay for the brand in comparison to other brands. The question asked was, “if your services provider increase the tariffs / retable but gives more value added service, what would you do?”

Options	Air Tel	Vodafone
(1) Continue with same company	34.38%	46.43%
(2) Continue with the same company even if you are dissatisfied	15.63%	14.29%
(3) Change over to the other company	37.5%	35.71%
(4) Discount using cell phones altogether	12.5%	3.57%

Price Premium

To measure the performance of the cellular provides employs an interesting classification to map the cell-phone users. The quadrants for this model are satisfaction on the Y-axis and loyalty on the X-axis.

RESULTS

PERCEIVED QUALITY

Low Clarity Sound	1	2	3	4	5	High Clarity Sound
Poor Connectivity						Good Connectivity
Poor Network						Good Network
Unfriendly Customer						Friendly Customer
Poor Service						Good Service

AIRTEL/VODAFONE

The semantic differential scale shows the differences in perceived quality between the service providers. Air Tel edges out Vodafone in terms of connectivity, network, and value added

services. There is not much of difference in the ratings because the respondents mostly gave average ratings.

Airtel

A majority of the respondents said that the advertisements of Air Tel came to their mind when they thought of Air Tel. Another common response was that Air Tel is a good service provider, if not the best. Some just thought of it as their mobile phone company. The other responses were service provider that helps connect people, technically advanced company, good coverage, power to connect people, making communication easy, user friendly, etc. One respondent even said Mr. Sunil Mittal (Chief of Bharti Enterprises) comes to his mind. Overall, Air Tel comes across as a competent and exciting brand.

CONCLUSION & IMPLICATIONS

Comparing Vodafone and Airtel on the Brand Equity Ten can conclude this study.

- 1. Price Premium:** Vodafone cell-phone service providers in terms of satisfied and loyal customers are willing to pay a price premium, while Air Tel leads with loyal but dissatisfied customers.
- 2. Satisfaction / Loyalty:** In terms of satisfaction, Air Tel leads with both very satisfied as well as satisfied customers. Dissatisfaction level is low.
- 3. Perceived Quality:** Here again, Air Tel edges out Vodafone in terms of connectivity, network and value added services. Vodafone leads in terms of clarity of sound and customer service.
- 4. Leadership and Popularity:** The results showed that majority of respondents chose Air Tel as the company with larger subscriber base compared to Vodafone Cell-phone. This reflected the “number one” syndrome where the leader must have merit.
- 5. Perceived Value:** The consistent responses by Vodafone Cell phone users perceive it as a value-for-money service. Air Tel is perceived to be expensive by its customers.
- 6. Brand Personality:** The brand personality of Air Tel comes across as an exciting and competent brand. Its vibrancy appeals to the customers who relate to the advertising messages.
- 7. Organizational Association:** Air Tel’s corporate brand is more visible than Vodafone. More respondents recognized the caption of Air Tel - Touch Tomorrow.

8. Brand Awareness: Brand awareness of the respondents was high with most being aware of both Air Tel and Vodafone. So the spoils are even for both the operators here.

9. Market Prices and Distribution Coverage: The market prices of the cellular service given by Air Tel and Vodafone are very similar. The difference if any is very marginal and is not considered. Also the distribution coverage is properly established. Therefore, there is not much to choose between the two operators and the spoils are even.

Comparing the overall findings we see that Air Tel leads in five brand equity measures (satisfaction/loyalty, perceived quality, leadership & popularity, organizational associations, market share). The other three measures (brand personality, brand awareness, market price and distribution coverage) have been shared by both Airtel and Vodafone. To conclude, the Brand Equity of Air Tel is higher than Vodafone, though marginally.

Recommendation of the study:

Air Tel

- ⇒ Many of the respondents perceived Air Tel's tariffs to be high. The company should focus its advertising message on this issue and compare it with the rival operator's tariffs (which are almost similar).
- ⇒ Air Tel should focus on those customers whose satisfaction is high but low loyalty. Loyalty based Programs should be introduced, which the company has introduced now in terms of Rewards Programmes. Also an alarming proportion of its customers are those with low satisfaction and low loyalty. This category poses a threat and their loyalty should be established.
- ⇒ In their advertising messages, Air Tel uses more than one caption "Touch Tomorrow" and "The Good Life". This creates Confusion in the customers mind. They should focus on their main line 'Touch Tomorrow. used in the Air Tel brand architecture.

Vodafone

Satisfaction levels of Vodafone Cell phone customers are comparatively lower than Air Tel customers. They should introduce reward-based schemes for its customers.

- ⇒ The company should build the brand on its price platform, where it enjoys an advantage over Air Tel in terms of customer's perceptions.
- ⇒ The advertising for its pre-paid brand, SPEED is very negligible. This should be pushed aggressively as the prepaid segment is the largest growing in the market.
- ⇒ Now in the market there is not much differentiation in terms of the basic mobile service. The only way to stand out is to give more onus on the Value Added Services (VAS) like WAP where Vodafone Cell phone is the pioneer.

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